

Research Article

**Incidence of Alzheimer's Disease in Type II Diabetes Mellitus
and Its associated Risk Factors of Development
of Dementia and Cognitive Decline**

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ABSTRACT

Objective:The purpose of this study is to explore the major risk factors for dementia and cognitive impairment in Alzheimer's disease after diabetes mellitus and to differentiate the Alzheimer's disease risk development in people with and without D.M.

Background:Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) may increase Alzheimer's disease (AD) specifically associated dementia risk through various biological pathways, but the relationship between DM and AD development remains unclear.

Place and Duration: The study was conducted in Endocrinology Department of Nishter Hospital, Multan for a period of 2 years from February 2012 to March 2014.

Methods:The reference test was conducted from February 2012 to March 2014 to determine the prevalence of common dementia in 401 cases of both sexes over 50 years of age. In all these cases Mini-Mental State Examination (MMSE) was performed. Blood glucose levels were randomly determined at each visit; A complete examination of all participants was performed clinically.

Results:In this study we came to the conclusion that with increases duration of diabetes, age and related conditions, over weight dementia increases. with diabetes Dementia increases and chi-square tests support the conclusions." The value of the statistic chi-square test calculated, corresponding to p, was 130.26 with a score of 9 .It was also considered that obesity diabetic patients had a greater chances of AD development, and participants with diabetes at the borderline were also at greater risk of AD development.

Conclusion:This study demonstrated that one of the greater risk factors that will increase AD risk is diabetes mellitus type 2; However, obesity may cause pathological problems in participants with Alzheimer's disease and cognitive and dementia decline markedly marked with other factors such as lifestyle and aging.

Key Words: Obesity, dementia, alzheimer's disease (AD), cognitive decline, Type-2 Diabetes mellitus (DMT2).

INTRODUCTION

Incidences have consistently shown that diabetes and perceptual deficits have a relationship between dementia, but not relationship, but the incidence of Alzheimer's disease has been intensively studied throughout world. studies of

different populations. In most of the diabetic patients insulin resistance is present and it is suggested that the mechanisms explore the Alzheimer's disease risk in patients of diabetic DM type 2 is associated with compulsory

hyperinsulinemia At present it is common in the elderly that may also be a determinant for cognitive and dementia impairment. Some evidence also supports the risk of borderline diabetes and dementia and Alzheimer's disease. Diabetes can contribute to poor memory as well as add many complications to the body and reduce intellectual brain functions in various ways. It is associated with pathophysiology as unhealthy lifestyles that can worsen hyperglycemia reported among some of the reasons that put our people at increased risk of obesity, daily stress, aging and memory problems, and we think of complications as age. the prevalence of diabetes can contribute to the increase in the Alzheimer's cases in the coming next years, Pakistan dramatically increases and is a major source of anxiety.

METHODOLOGY:

a Men and women 50 years or older.

b Memory loss complaints are difficult to memorize the names of people after such entry, difficulty to remember phone numbers or codes, problems that are explored in everyday issues such as difficulty in taking multiple tasks or remembering several items Difficulty in getting postcards and information quickly or keeping track of attention. Loss of memory in the beginning should be considered as a circumspect phenomenon without any deterioration suddenly in the last few months.

Diabetic and diabetic dementia.

To determine the prevalence of dementia in this study, 401 people over 50 years of age were included. In all these cases Mini-Mental State Examination (MMSE) was performed. We consider a series of 21-30 normal to 21-30 cognitive cognition that is mild dementia, although we accept 10-20 heavier <10 demented middle dementia and patients. Older patients who are non-diabetic (n = 188) and diabetes (n = 212) for this study were selected of (age > 50 years). All participants with initial diagnosis of AS underwent extensive cognitive testing and clinical examination as determined previously. The DA diagnosis is homogenous to the international

criteria¹⁵ and necessitates a progressive deterioration, tardive onset, and absence of peculiar causes of dementia. Mini-Review Mental State Assessment (MMSE) The Stroke-Alzheimer's Association and Related Disorders (NINCDS), all of which are conducted on these issues while for identifying Alzheimer's disease our criteria is same and communicative used by the National Institute of Neurological Disorders. The ADRA). Blood glucose levels were randomly determined at each visit, and almost no pain was felt with ACCU-CHEK-Active Glucometer. Patients were followed for dementia scores and cognitive impairment. Analysis of the patients Statistically is based on event schedules to assess the relation between the absence or presence of diabetes or without diabetes and was decided by the Chi-square test for autonomy between variables.

RESULTS:

With the duration of diabetes the risk of "dementia" increases and test chi-square confirm the affirm. The value calculated of the statistics of chi-square test was 131.06, with a freedom 9 degree, analogous to the value of p (<0.006).

DISCUSSION:

Diabetes is considered as a common disorder of metabolic pathway in Pakistan, with other risk factors such as cardiovascular problems and obesity. In elderly people, however dementia is a cognitive problem when neurologically perceive with AD in patients of diabetes mellitus. The previous hypothesis has been formulated that changes in diabetes, obesity and related insulin resistance, perhaps at insulin receptors, may contribute to a decrease in insulin sensitivity, which may reduce synaptic plasticity at aging. These consequences seems because of a high level of insulin in the brain as observed in obesity, diabetes and aging which reduces amyloid A B clearance, thereby amyloid toxicity increases. However, there is a continuing lack of information about the appliance that may result in cognitive impairment functions in hyperglycaemic patients.

Dementia vs. Diabetes duration

		Diabetes Duration			
		1-5 yrs	6-10 yrs	11-15 yrs	16-20 yrs
Dementia	+	67%	19%	0%	0%
	++	31%	33%	22%	0%
	+++	3%	48%	78%	86%
	++++	0%	0%	0%	14%

Tendency of Dementia by Diabetic Duration

According to advanced studies, it is unlikely that the abilities confounding the demographic effects variables, such as gender or age, socioeconomic status or educational status is the relationship between diabetes and dementia. In addition, the standard neuropsychological routines seen in these patients may be associated with cerebrovascular disease complications, which may be related to the result of various pathological processes that develop within the period of the disease, the harmful hyperglycaemic effects on the brain are known as the main cause of the reduction in perception, reaction duration and processing. It has been supposed that the diabetes mellitus duration is primary cause for insulin signaling changes that could be a major hyperglycemic cells of brain cause of damaging effects such as nerve cell death, damaged blood vessels or deposits amyloid acquisition. When compared to our non-diabetic and non-obese individuals, most people with

obese diabetes were found to have primarily memory problems.

Showing relationship of BMI and occurrence of Dementia in both Diabetic & Non-Diabetic Population

The numbers of real patients of diabetes mellitus is higher in our population, but fewer patients develop dementia, which limits statistical analysis for the recognition of such risk factors for dementia in this subset. In our study, we came to the conclusion that in a sample of elderly individuals with basal diabetes, clinical cognitive impairment became a common event and was estimated by a decrease in cognitive functions. These findings have potential clinical presence and require more validated studies in diabetic and non-diabetic populations. However, obesity and controls over the rising tendency of diabetes or hyperglycemia can help to minimize the harmful effects of the brain and its functions on our population.

CONCLUSION:

In our study, "Type 2 diabetes" is an important factor (disease) to increase AD risk in Pakistan; along with other factors such as obesity, lifestyle and aging. Long-term diabetes can lead to Alzheimer's disease and related pathological conditions in people with dementia and cognitive impairment. Some limitations of our work deserve more debate. Our epidemiological observations, together with the empirical evidence that emerges, support the possible role of diabetes in the pathogenesis of AD. Our data also increase the likelihood that obesity and related factors such as

gender, age and lifestyles can provide a link and may be useful for early detection of risks and prevention of AD and related dementia.

REFERENCES:

- 1 Alzheimer's A. 2015 Alzheimer's disease facts and figures. *Alzheimer's & dementia: the journal of the Alzheimer's Association*. 2015 Mar;11(3):332.
- 2 Alzheimer A. A Characteristic Disease of the Cerebral Cortex: Meeting of South-West Germany Psychiatrists Held in Tubingen on November 3rd and 4th, 1906. 1907.
- 3 Braak, H. and Braak, E., 1991. Neuropathological staging of Alzheimer-related changes. *Acta neuropathologica*, 82(4), pp.239-259.
- 4 Dominguez D, Tournoy J, Hartmann D, Huth T, Cryns K, Deforce S, Serneels L, Camacho IE, Marjaux E, Craessaerts K, Roebroek AJ. Phenotypic and biochemical analyses of BACE1-and BACE2-deficient mice. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*. 2005 Sep 2;280(35):30797-806.
- 5 Strittmatter WJ, Saunders AM, Schmechel D, Pericak-Vance M, Enghild J, Salvesen GS, Roses AD. Apolipoprotein E: high-avidity binding to beta-amyloid and increased frequency of type 4 allele in late-onset familial Alzheimer disease. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*. 1993 Mar 1;90(5):1977-81.
- 6 Farrer, L.A., Cupples, L.A., Haines, J.L., Hyman, B., Kukull, W.A., Mayeux, R., Myers, R.H., Pericak-Vance, M.A., Risch, N. and Van Duijn, C.M., 1997. Effects of age, sex, and ethnicity on the association between apolipoprotein E genotype and Alzheimer disease: a meta-analysis. *Jama*, 278(16), pp.1349-1356.
- 7 Masters CL, Simms G, Weinman NA, Multhaup G, McDonald BL, Beyreuther K. Amyloid plaque core protein in Alzheimer disease and Down syndrome. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*. 1985 Jun 1;82(12):4245-9.
- 8 Schenk D, Barbour R, Dunn W, Gordon G, Grajeda H, Guido T, Hu K, Huang J, Johnson-Wood K, Khan K, Kholodenko D. Immunization with amyloid- β attenuates Alzheimer-disease-like pathology in the PDAPP mouse. *Nature*. 1999 Jul;400(6740):173.
- 9 Grundke-Iqbal I, Iqbal K, Tung YC, Quinlan M, Wisniewski HM, Binder LI. Abnormal phosphorylation of the microtubule-associated protein tau (tau) in Alzheimer cytoskeletal pathology. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*. 1986 Jul 1;83(13):4913-7.
- 10 Seeger T, Fedorova I, Zheng F, Miyakawa T, Koustova E, Gomeza J, Basile AS, Alzheimer C, Wess J. M2 muscarinic acetylcholine receptor knock-out mice show deficits in behavioral flexibility, working memory, and hippocampal plasticity. *Journal of Neuroscience*. 2004 Nov 10;24(45):10117-27.
- 11 Werner S, Alzheimer C. Roles of activin in tissue repair, fibrosis, and inflammatory disease. *Cytokine & growth factor reviews*. 2006 Jun 1;17(3):157-71.
- 12 Werner S, Alzheimer C. Roles of activin in tissue repair, fibrosis, and inflammatory disease. *Cytokine & growth factor reviews*. 2006 Jun 1;17(3):157-71.
- 13 Lipowsky R, Gillessen T, Alzheimer C. Dendritic Na⁺ channels amplify EPSPs in hippocampal CA1 pyramidal cells. *Journal of Neurophysiology*. 1996 Oct 1;76(4):2181-91.
- 14 Sydow A, Van der Jeugd A, Zheng F, Ahmed T, Balschun D, Petrova O, Drexler D, Zhou L, Rune G, Mandelkow E, D'Hooge R. Tau-induced defects in synaptic plasticity, learning, and memory are reversible in transgenic mice after switching off the toxic Tau mutant. *Journal of Neuroscience*. 2011 Feb 16;31(7):2511-25.